

电子和正电子的可能结构

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摘要: 本文作者认为电子是有结构的, 不是数学上的点。因此电子的体积是有限的, 不是无穷小量。由于电子具有磁矩和自旋, 其空间分布也不是各向同性的。提出的电子和正电子结构模型, 环光子结构模型, 即电子和正电子是由环形的光子构成的, 并指出其与基能即基本能量、物质和光子间的内在联系。通过对电子和正电子湮灭及产生过程的深入研究, 能在更深层次研究和理解静止质量和物质的起源和根源, 尤其是在失去光速则获得静止质量而失去静止质量则获得光速的转换过程中。这意味着, 任何东西获得静止质量必须失去光速, 而获得光速必须失去其静止质量。这深入揭示出静止质量和光速的内在关系和自然规律。提出一个用有序运动判断物质与基能的标准。即物质是有序运动的基能构成的, 而无序运动的基能使其仍处于基能状态。可能证据包括: 基能流的可能碰撞创造正负电子对, 正负电子对湮灭产生的两个光子的相干性且这两个光子的光子周期数应该均为偶数, 电子或正电子近电场在空间中可能的非各向同性分布, 由于基能分布和变化引起的引力场的异常改变, 由于引力场突然和剧烈的改变使基能可能产生有序的物质如粒子等。所有这些证据都能用实验检验和证实。

关键词: 电子结构, 正电子结构, 环光子, 静止质量和光速, 电子和正电子湮灭, 基能

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电子是结构最简单的粒子之一并在物理和多数科学研究的许多理论模型和实验中被假设为点粒子。理论和实验都证实电子不是一个没有任何体积的数学点, 因此可以假设它的体积是有限的, 而不是无穷小的。在这有限的体积内, 电子的磁矩和自旋表明如果电子内有任何分布, 则其空间分布不是各向同性的。所以电子应该存在内部结构。

考虑电子和正电子湮灭生成光子对的物理现象并进行深入的研究。忽略相对很弱的引力, 它们相互间只有电磁相互作用, 没有强和弱相互作用。电子又是最简单的粒子。当电子与正电子相遇时, 由于电磁相互作用产生的引力, 使它们相互接近到表面接触的程度, 如果认为它们有表面, 然后相互破坏彼此的组成结构, 生成一对新的光子。

在这个从接触到破坏的动态过程中, 我们想要分析的事实包括它们静止质量的消失、它们彼此可能破坏的是对方什么样的结构、静止质量如何转换成光子的能量、电子或正电子稳定存在的机制或锁模方式、有几种结构破坏方式? 电子或正电子的静电场或电属性是怎么消失的以及在正负电子对的产生中又是如何产生的? 这种静电场又是什么物质的分布? 这是理论和实验面临的一个巨大挑战。

电子和正电子的一个可能结构是环光子。可以认为是单个光子的首尾连接起来构成一个闭环的光子, 即环光子, 同时生成一个粒子, 例如一个电子[1]。生

成粒子的整体结构是一个具有近圆形横截面的旋转体。环光子的波矢量沿着圆做环绕运动，或处在静止不动状态。电子结构是由环光子沿着圆环轴向的纵向做闭环运动形成且其相位正好使其电场矢量指向内。正电子结构是像电子结构那样的环光子但其电场矢量指向外。由此它们构成具有正负电荷的不同电场并互相吸引。见图 1。电子或正电子的频率数是偶数，因此当电场向环中心移动时就相互抵消。仅当电场离开环中心向外移动时，不论其矢量指向内或外都存在。这些电场由位相差 π 形成正电子的正电场和电子的负电场。另一方面，由于无法分辨，也可以认为环光子构成的电子和正电子整体是处于静止状态。

图 1 电子和正电子的可能结构。 (a)由偶数频率，这里假设为 40，构成的电子和正电子的可能结构。电子结构是其环光子电场矢量指向内而正电子结构是指向外。(b)由一个环光子形成电子和正电子电场的机制。把圆环展开排成两行是为了展示其电场相互抵消的效果。

当电子与正电子相遇时，破坏的结构正是其闭合环状运动的结构，其正负电荷消失是由于两个相反方向电场的结合或恢复成它们原来的中性状态。见图 1。

再考虑电子和正电子对的产生过程。例如一个高能粒子与物质相互作用首先产生一个中性能量场，然后这个能量场分裂成两部分生成电子和正电子对。这里我们认为或假设先产生一个特殊有序闭环运动的能量场再生成电子和正电子对。同时分裂的环电场矢量指向内时生成电子而指向外时生成正电子，并同时使电子和正电子对具有其负正电荷和电特性。

由电磁相互作用生产的能量场开始独立移动，并且，如果它独自沿着直线移动则生成一个以光速传播的光子，如果它绕闭环运动则生成一对电子和正电子并获得静止质量同时失去其光速。因此电子或正电子的质心运动就构成同时也是具有静止质量的普通刚体运动。

通过电子和正电子湮灭和产生过程，能对静止质量和物质的起源进行深入研究，尤其是对失去其光速则获得其静止质量及失去其静止质量则获得其光速的过程。在湮灭过程中，一对电子和正电子失去其静止质量变为两个光子并获得其光

速，而在产生过程中，能量场失去其光速产生一对电子和正电子并使它们获得静止质量。原子的静止质量和一个光子的高速可以通过电磁相互作用转换。例如一个光子被原子吸收，光子失去其光速而原子的静止质量增加，而对于发射则相反。

在这种动态产生过程中，从产生能量场到其分裂生成电子和正电子对，上述分析表明的事实是任何物质获得其静止质量必须失去其光速，而获得其光速必须失去其静止质量。这深层次揭示出静止质量和光速间的本质关系。从中性到正负电荷的分裂机制，在电子和正电子对形成中由其相位产生的电子或正电子的静电场或特征。因此生成电子和正电子的结构可能就是闭环光子。

另一种电子和正电子的可能结构是，在极微小尺度上，如远小于 10^{-17} 米，能量的一种闭环结构。假设其是基能即基本能量构成的圆环。电子是基能沿圆环的轴线方向的纵向做闭合环状运动构成，而正电子是基能沿圆环的轴线方向的横向做闭合环状运动构成，见图 2。并由此产生两种不同的电场，即正负电子的电场。由这种纵向比横向运动模式更容易实现，能解释自然界中产生的电子比正电子总量多很多的起源和成因。

图 2 电子和正电子的可能结构。它们可能是，在极微小尺度上，如远小于 10^{-17} 米，基能的一种闭环结构。(a)电子结构是基能沿圆环的轴线方向的纵向做闭合环状运动构成。(b)正电子结构是基能沿圆环的轴线方向的横向做闭合环状运动构成。

电子和正电子湮灭和产生过程是一个动态转换过程，其中，基能的结构模式是从闭环运动转换到振动并沿直线传播的结构模式。光子可认为是基能的振动并沿直线运动的结构模式。

我们研究的结论是光子、电子和正电子等都是基能不同运动方式的一种外在表现模式。只有基能的特殊运动模式才是可见或可测量的。用有序运动作为物质和基能的一个判断标准就是物质是基能的有序运动而基能的无序运动使其仍保持在基能状态。

支持这些结论的可能证据，包括实验检验，例如基能流间可能的碰撞产生正负电子对，或其它的粒子和反粒子对。若假设正负电子各自破坏后分别生成一个光子，即电子生成一个而正电子生成另一个光子，则这两个光子应该有很大的不同，并携带有来自湮灭正负电子对的信息。例如其运动模式应该不同，而且所有正负电子对湮灭生成的光子对，应该具有相同的运动模式差异，其相关性表现应一致。如初始和普通相位差、相对位置差等。再有就是由于来自不同光源，这两个光子应该是不相干的。如果相干则表明它们来自同一光源，即正负电子对湮灭时是先形成一个整体再分裂形成二个光子。以及电子或正电子近电场空间分布的可能不均匀性，也是其存在结构的可能证据。引力场使光线弯曲。由于基能分布

和变化导致的引力场不规则的变化，可能的有序事例例如由于引力场突然和强的变化而由基能产生的粒子，也是可能的证据。所有这些证据都能用实验检验。

总结，我们已经提出电子和正电子的一种可能结构以及基能、物质和光子间的可能内存关系。我们的结论是电子和正电子的体积是有限的并且都有一个确定的表面或界面。提出物质是基能的有序运动而基能的无序运动使其仍保持在基能状态。为这些结论提供的可能证据是基能流的可能碰撞创造正负电子对，正负电子对湮灭产生的两个光子的不同相干性且这两个光子的光子周期数应该均为偶数，电子或正电子近电场在空间中可能的非各向同性分布。所有这些证据都能用实验检验和证实。通过对电子和正电子湮灭及产生过程的深入研究，我们发现光速和静止质量间的关键关系，并能在更深层次研究静止质量和物质的起源，尤其是在失去光速则获得静止质量而失去静止质量则获得光速的转换过程中。

Possible structure of electron and positron

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Abstract

We think and assume the electron is of structure and not a mathematical point, so the volume of an electron is limited, not infinitesimal, and the distribution is inhomogeneous in space due to its magnetic moment and spin. Here we show a possible structure of electron and positron, and the possible relationship among Jineng, matter and photons. By the electron and positron annihilation and production processes, the origin of rest mass and matter can be deeply investigated and understood, especially on the processes, lost the velocity of light then obtained the rest mass and lost the rest mass then obtained the velocity of light. It means anything to obtain the rest mass must lose the velocity of light, and to obtain the velocity of light must lose its rest mass. That deeply reveals the nature relationship between the rest mass and the velocity of light. One judge criteria for the matter and Jineng by the ordered motions is suggested. The matter is the ordered motions of Jineng and the random motions of Jineng remain in Jineng state. Potential evidences are possible collisions of Jineng flows to create electron-positron pairs, the coherent characteristic of the two photons produced by the electron and positron annihilation and the photon period number of these two photons should be even, the possible inhomogeneous near-electric field distribution of electron or positron in space, the gravitational field abnormal changes due to Jineng distribution and changes, possible ordered things such as particles produced by Jineng due to the sudden and strong changes of gravitational fields. All these evidences can be tested experimentally.

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Keywords: electron structure, positron structure, loop-photon, rest mass and velocity of light, electron and positron annihilation, Jineng

Electrons are one of the simplest particles in structure and assumed as a point particle in many theoretical models and experiments in physics researches and most scientific investigations. Both theory and experiment confirm that an electron is not a mathematical point without any volume, so we can assume that the volume of an electron is limited, not infinitesimal. In this limited volume, the magnetic moment and spin of an electron indicates that if there is anything distribution in the electron, then the distribution is inhomogeneous in space. Therefore, there should be of structure in the electron.

We take the physical phenomenon of electron and positron annihilation becoming a pair of photons into account and try to investigate it deeply. There is only electromagnetic interaction between them and without the strong and weak interactions, if we omit the relative very weak gravitational effect. When an electron encounters a positron, due to the attraction produced by the electromagnetic interaction, they approach to the degree of surface contact with each other if they have a surface, then mutually destroy their forming structure, produce a new pair of photons.

In this dynamic procedure, from the contact of electron and positron to their structure broken, we try to analyze the facts include their rest masses to disappear, what kind of structure destroyed, the rest mass transforms into the energy of photons, the mechanism or locked mode of electron and positron exists stably, and how many modes are there to destroy their structures? How does the electrostatic field or characteristic feature of an electron or positron disappear and how is it produced in the electron and positron pair formation? What matter distribution does form this kind of electrostatic field? That is a great challenge to both theory and experiment.

One possible structure of electron and positron could be the loop-photon, i.e. the begin and end of a single photon are connected to form a closed loop-photon, and to form a particle, e.g. an electron [1]. The integral structure is a rotary body with near circle cross section. The wave vector of loop-photon moves along the circle doing circulatory motion, or in motionless position. The electron structure is formed by the loop-photon to move along the longitudinal direction of axial direction of circular ring to do closed loop motion and the phase just makes the electric field vector to point in. The positron structure is the loop-photon as the electron structure but with the electric field vector to point out. So they form different electric fields with positive and negative charges, and attractive with each other. See Fig. 1. The number of frequency of electron or positron is even so when the

FIG. 1: (Color online) (a) Possible structure of electron and positron formed by a loop-photon with even frequency number, of 40 assumed here. The electron structure is the electric field vector of loop-photon to point in and the positron structure is to point out. (b) Mechanism forming the electric fields of electron and positron by a loop-photon. Put the loop into two lines to show the cancel effect of electric fields.

electric fields moving towards the loop center it is canceled itself. Only the electric fields moving towards out of the loop center it is left despite the vector points in or out. These fields form the positive electric fields of positron and the negative electric fields of electron by the phase difference of π . On the other hand, we can think the loop-photon forming electrons and positrons is in motionless position due to undistinguishable.

When the electron and positron encounter, the broken structures are their closed loop structure, and their negative and positive charges disappear due to combination of two electric fields with opposite direction or restore their original neutral states, see Fig. 1.

We take the production procedure of an electron and positron pair into account, e.g. a high energy particle interacts with matter to produce an neutral energy-field first then this

energy-field splits into two parts to form an electron and positron pair. Here we think or assume to produce one energy-field first and the electron and positron pair is produced by the same split energy-field which is specially ordered loop motion. The split loop electric field vector pointing in forms an electron and pointing out forms a positron simultaneously and makes the electron and positron pair to have their negative and positive charges and electric properties.

The energy-field produced by electromagnetic interaction, begins to move independently, and if it moves along with a straight line then forms a photon to propagate with the velocity of light, if it moves around the closed circle then forms a pair of electron and positron to get the rest mass and lose the velocity of light. So the center of mass motion of electrons or positrons is general rigid body motion with the rest mass.

By the electron and positron annihilation and production process, the origin of rest mass and matter can be deeply investigated, especially on the processes of lost the velocity of light then obtained the rest mass and lost the rest mass then obtained the velocity of light. In the annihilation process, a pair of electron and positron loses the rest mass to become two photons and obtain the velocity of light, and in the production process, the energy-field loses the velocity of light to produce a pair of electron and positron and make them obtain the rest mass. The atomic rest mass and the velocity of light of a photon can convert by electromagnetic interaction. For example, a photon is absorbed by an atom, the photon loses the velocity of light and the atomic rest mass increases, and for emitted inversely.

In this dynamic production procedure, from the energy-field produced to it splits to form an electron and positron pair, above analyses indicate the facts that anything to obtain the rest mass must lose the velocity of light, and to obtain the velocity of light must lose its rest mass. That deeply reveals the nature relationship between the rest mass and the velocity of light. The energy-field transforms into the rest mass of electron and positron pair just by losing its velocity of light. The splitting mechanism from neutral to negative and positive charges, and the electrostatic fields or characteristic feature of an electron or positron produced in the electron and positron pair formation is by their phase. The electron and positron structure produced would be the loop-photons.

Another kind of electron and positron structure, on the extreme micro scale, such as far less than 10^{-17} meter, a sort of closed loop structure of Jineng is suggested. We suppose it is a circular ring formed by Jineng. Electrons are formed by Jineng to move along the

FIG. 2: (Color online) Possible structure of electron and positron. They could be, on the extreme micro scale, such as far less than 10^{-17} meter, a sort of closed loop structure of Jineng. (a) The electron structure is formed by Jineng to move along the longitudinal direction of axial direction of circular ring to do closed loop motion. (b) The positron structure is Jineng along the transverse direction of axial direction of circular ring to do closed loop motion.

longitudinal direction of axial direction of circular ring to do closed loop motion, whereas positrons are Jineng along the transverse direction of axial direction of circular ring to do closed loop motion, see Fig. 2. And thereof they create two kinds of different electrical fields, namely the electrical fields of electron and positron. By this, we could explain the origin that electrons are much more than positrons in nature with such longitudinal direction motion to create easier than the transversal motion mode.

Whereas the electron and positron annihilation and production process is a dynamic conversion process in which the structure model of Jineng transforms from the closed loop motion to the vibration and propagation in a straight line.

Conclusions are photons, electrons and positrons and more, all are a sort of representative module of the different modes of motions of Jineng. Only the special modes of motions of Jineng are visible or measurable. One judge criteria for the matter and Jineng by the ordered motions is that the matter is the ordered motions of Jineng and the random motions of Jineng remain in Jineng state.

Potential evidences for these conclusions, include experimental verifications, such as possible collisions of Jineng flows to create electron-positron pairs, or other particle and antiparticle pairs. If we suppose that the structure of electron and positron are broken itself

then convert to a photon each other, i.e. the electron converts to the first photon and the positron converts to the second photon, then these two photons must be quite different, and carry the information from the annihilated electron-positron pairs. Such as the motion modes of these two photons should differ, furthermore all photon pairs produced by the electron-positron pair annihilation, should possess the same difference in motion mode, their correlativity should behave the same way, such as initial and normal phase difference, relative location difference and more. Other evidence, these two photons should be noncoherent due to coming from different light sources. And if they are coherent, they must come from the same light source. This coherence indicates that when the electron-positron pairs annihilate they first form a body and then split into two photons. The possible inhomogeneous near-electrical field distribution of electron or positron in space is possible structure evidence. The gravitational field makes the light to bend. The gravitational field abnormal changes due to Jineng distribution and changes, possible ordered things such as particles produced by Jineng due to the sudden and strong changes of gravitational fields, are possible evidences too. All these evidences can be tested experimentally.

In summary, we have suggested a possible structure of electron and positron, and the possible relationship among Jineng, matter and photons. We conclude that the volume of electron and positron is limited and electron and positron have a definite surface or boundary. The matter is the ordered motions of Jineng and the random motions of Jineng remain in Jineng state is suggested. Potential evidences for these conclusions are possible collisions of Jineng flows to create electron-positron pairs, the different coherence of the two photons produced by the electron and positron annihilation and the photon period number of these two photons should be even, the possible inhomogeneous near-electric field distribution of electron or positron in space. All these evidences can be tested experimentally. By the electron and positron annihilation and production process, we find the key relationship between the velocity of light and the rest mass, and investigate the origin of rest mass and matter deeply, especially on the processes of lost the velocity of light then obtained the rest mass and lost the rest mass then obtained the velocity of light.

[1] Bao-Guo Dong, Pei Dong, Ji-Yuan Gu, Photon structure and characteristics. Unpublished.